

TRAINING OF TRAINERS PROGRAM

EDUCATIONAL PROJECT

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EDUCATIONAL PROJECT

1. Characterization:

Teacher's Name:	Mitzy Mariley Marín Monterrey ORCID: https://orcid.org/0009-0008-3993-0455
School's Name:	Pedro Pablo Sanchez Junior - High School
Name of the Educational Project:	Pedagogical Practices and Technological Integration for teaching English
Province:	Panama Oeste
Language Skill(s) to Strength:	Listening, Speaking, Reading and writing
Objective:	To implement the effectiveness of integrating pedagogical practices with technology for students to improve the learning experience and facilitate English language acquisition.

2. Description of the Documental Exploration:

The exploration of relevant literature for the educational project involved a meticulous review of recent academic articles and resources from platforms such as Mendeley, Scielo, Semantic Scholar, Typeset, Scopus and ScienceDirect. Key studies from 2019 to 2024 were identified, focusing on innovative pedagogical practices and the integration of technology in English language teaching.

CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) is an educational approach that integrates curricular content taught through a foreign language, promoting interaction in that language within the classroom. The term emerged in the mid-1990s, building on earlier practices of content-based language instruction from the 1960s in Canadian and U.S. schools. CLIL is characterized as a “dual-focused approach,” giving equal importance to both language and content, allowing students to learn the language naturally while acquiring knowledge in various subjects, ultimately preparing them for a multilingual and global society. (Tavernise, 2020)

Besides, Smith et al. (2021), “Emphasized the effectiveness of blended learning environments in enhancing student engagement”.

Moreover, this model allows students to interact with content in a more dynamic way, fostering personalized and collaborative learning experiences. Consequently, the research by Smith et al. emphasizes the critical need to innovate educational methodologies to maximize student potential in an increasingly digital world.

According to Dişlen Dağgöl, G. (2022):

Teaching and learning evolve, English teachers must use new methods and technological tools for enhanced language teaching in the digital era. The use of technology is essential in learning a foreign language and although the technology is already in student pockets, mounted on walls, and in nearly all electronic device in the back of classrooms, many teachers often overlook how to leverage and integrate it as a didactic resource for their language teaching and language instructions.

One of the difficulties of integrating digital technologies into education is the limited availability of digital resources in educational institutions, as reported in research that shows that when available in public elementary schools, the use of technological resources is controlled and restricted. These restrictions may hamper the integration of digital technology in public education widening the digital gap between formal education and everyday life. School access to internet can foster the development of individual's autonomy in search for information to narrow the digital gap. (Mendes & finardi, 2020)

Additionally, Garcia (2023), “Explored the impact of mobile applications on language acquisition, highlighting their role in facilitating personalized learning experience”.

As stated by Jones & Richards (2020) in their book, *Creativity in Language Teaching: Perspectives from Research and Practice*, creativity is strongly linked to motivational issues, such that both creative teachers and students are more motivated and engaged in their work. Moreover, the creative teacher is original and highly valued and followed by students. Clearly, this teacher is at an advantage in fostering creative students. The authors define creativity in its main aspects: novelty, originality, and problem-solving ability; they relate it to culture and language teaching, and emphasize the essential role of creativity in creating new learning environments inside and outside the classroom, thus providing new learning opportunities through digital technology, humanistic learning, and the benefits of languages for individuals and society.

In conclusion, the literature reviewed for this educational project underscores the pivotal role of innovative pedagogical practices and technology integration in enhancing English language teaching. The findings from various studies, including the emphasis on blended learning by Smith et al. (2021) and the insights from Dişlen Dağgöl (2022) regarding the necessity for teachers to embrace new methods, highlight a clear call to action for educators. Despite challenges such as limited access to digital resources and the digital divide, the potential for technology to foster personalized learning experiences is evident, as noted by Garcia (2023). Furthermore, the importance of creativity in teaching, as articulated by Jones & Richards (2020), reinforces the idea that engaging and original educators can significantly motivate students. Overall, this exploration reveals that by harnessing technology and fostering creativity, educators can create dynamic and effective learning environments that prepare students for the demands of the digital age.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that CLIL approach included blended learning, technological tools among others. It is a student-centred strategy that is used to integrate subject area curriculum, extracurricular activities and foreign language instruction into one teaching practice. As a result, it improves motivation in the language and the subject, it promotes higher-order skills and critical thinking.

3. Description of the Outlining Process

This outline process, designed to address New Pedagogical Practices and Technological Integration for teaching English, has been carefully crafted with three specific objectives in mind. By focusing on innovative teaching strategies and the effective use of technology, this framework aims to enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. Each component of the outline aligns with our overarching goals, ensuring a cohesive approach that empowers both educators and learners in the English language classroom. Through this initiative, we strive to create a dynamic learning environment that not only embraces modern pedagogical methods but also fosters a deeper connection between students and the material.

Module #1: Engaging Students through Innovative Pedagogical Practices

Objective: Design pedagogical practices (e.g., CLIL, flipped classroom, gamification, digital tools, project-based learning, and so on) combined with technology to enhance student engagement and motivation in the English language classroom.

Module Overview:

This module will introduce students to various innovative pedagogical practices and demonstrate how these can be effectively integrated with technology to foster a more engaging and motivating learning environment.

1. Teacher Actions:

1.1 Introduction to Pedagogical Practices:

- Present an overview of each pedagogical practice (CLIL, flipped classroom, gamification, digital tools, project-based learning,) using multimedia presentations.
- Share real-life examples that illustrate the effectiveness of these practices.

1.2 Demonstration of Technology Integration:

- Conduct live demonstrations of digital tools (e.g., Microsoft team, Moodle, Miro, Mentimeter, Edpuzzle, Padlet, Canva, Blackbox) that support these pedagogical practices.
- Show how to create interactive lessons using gamification techniques or digital tools.

1.3 Guided Activities:

- Organize group activities where students experience a flipped classroom setup, where they review materials at home and engage in collaborative activities in class.

- Facilitate project-based learning sessions where students work on real-world problems using CLIL approaches.

1.4 Feedback and Reflection:

- Encourage students to reflect on their experiences with each practice through guided discussions.
- Provide feedback on their participation and engagement during activities.

2. Student Actions:

2.1 Engagement with Content:

- Actively participate in discussions and share their prior experiences with traditional and innovative teaching methods.
- Explore the provided digital tools and resources to understand their functionalities.

2.2 Collaborative Learning:

- Work in groups to design projects that incorporates technology.
- Participate in a flipped classroom activity by reviewing assigned materials at home and coming prepared for in-class discussions.

2.3 Project-Based Learning:

- Engage in a project where they apply the principles of CLIL to create a presentation or a product related to a specific topic (e.g., environmental issues, cultural studies, robotic projects, wearable technology projects, and research projects).
- Use digital tools to collaborate with peers, share resources, and present their findings.

2.4 Reflection and Feedback:

- Reflect on their learning experiences through journals or discussion posts, focusing on how the new practices impacted their engagement and motivation.
- Provide feedback on the effectiveness of the pedagogical practices and technology used in the classroom.

In conclusion, this module aims to equip students with a comprehensive understanding of innovative pedagogical practices and their integration with technology, fostering an engaging and motivating learning environment in the English language classroom.

Module #2: Innovative Learning

Objective: Implement the use of pedagogical practices combined with technology to enhance student engagement and motivation in the English language classroom.

1. Teacher Actions:

1.1 Preparation and Planning:

- Design lesson plans that integrate new pedagogical practices (e.g., flipped classroom, gamification, project-based learning) with appropriate technology tools.
- Create a resource bank of digital tools and platforms that can be used for each practice.

1.2 Instruction and Modeling:

- Introduce each pedagogical practice through direct instruction, explaining its benefits and how it can enhance learning.
- Model the use of technology in real-time, demonstrating how to navigate and utilize tools effectively.

1.3 Facilitation of Activities:

- Facilitate hands-on activities where students can practice using the new pedagogical methods with technology.
- Provide guidance and support as students work on collaborative projects or engage in gamified learning experiences.

1.4 Assessment and Feedback:

- Develop assessment criteria that reflect the integration of pedagogical practices and technology.
- Offer constructive feedback on student performance and engagement during activities.

2. Student Actions:

2.1 Active Participation:

- Engage in discussions about the new pedagogical practices and their potential impact on learning.
- Explore and familiarize themselves with the technology tools introduced by the teacher.

2.2 Application of Practices:

- Participate in activities that utilize the flipped classroom model, preparing materials at home and collaborating in class.
- Engage in gamified learning experiences, applying concepts through interactive games and quizzes.

2.3 Collaborative Projects:

- Work in groups to design and execute a project that incorporates project-based learning principles using digital tools.
- Present their projects to the class, showcasing their understanding of both the content and the pedagogical practices used.

2.4 Reflection and Evaluation:

- Reflect on their experiences with the new practices and technology through journals or group discussions.
- Provide feedback on the effectiveness of the integration of technology in enhancing their learning experience.

To sum up, this module aims to actively implement innovative didactical, pedagogical practices combined with technology, fostering a dynamic and engaging learning environment that enhances student participation and motivation.

Module #3: Assessing Impact: Evaluating Students' Perceptions of Technology in Learning.

Objective: evaluate students' perceptions of pedagogical and technological integration in their learning to enhance student engagement and motivation in the English language classroom.

1. Teacher Actions:

1.1 Introduction to Evaluation Methods:

- Explain the importance of evaluating perceptions of technology in education.
- Introduce various methods for gathering feedback (surveys, discussions, reflective journals).

1.2 Designing Evaluation Tools:

- Create and distribute surveys or questionnaires that assess students' experiences with technology integration.
- Prepare prompts for reflective journals focusing on specific aspects of technology use in the classroom.

1.3 Facilitating Discussions:

- Organize focus group discussions to gather qualitative feedback on students' perceptions.
- Encourage open dialogue about what technologies they found helpful or challenging.

1.4 Analyzing Feedback:

- Collect and analyze survey results and discussion notes to identify trends and insights.
- Share findings with students, highlighting areas of success and opportunities for improvement.

2. Student Actions:

2.1 Engagement in Evaluation Activities:

- Complete surveys or questionnaires honestly, reflecting on their experiences with technology in learning.
- Participate in focus group discussions, sharing their thoughts and feelings about the integration of technology.

2.2 Reflective Journaling:

- Maintain a reflective journal documenting their experiences with technological tools in the classroom, focusing on engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes.
- Respond to specific prompts about how technology has impacted their learning.

2.3 Providing Constructive Feedback:

- Offer constructive feedback during discussions, highlighting specific technologies or practices that enhanced or hindered their learning.
- Suggest improvements or additional tools they believe would be beneficial.

2.4 Collaborative Reflection:

- Work in small groups to discuss their perceptions and summarize their collective insights to share with the class.

- Present their reflections on how technology has shaped their learning experiences.

In short, this module focuses on evaluating students' perceptions of technological integration in their learning, fostering a culture of feedback and continuous improvement in teaching practices. By actively engaging in the evaluation process, students contribute to enhancing the learning environment.

4. Type of Project: Innovation Project

This educational project involves the creation of an interactive teaching guide designed to integrate New Pedagogical Practices and Technological Tools for teaching English. The guide will serve as a comprehensive resource for educators, providing step-by-step instructions, practical activities, and digital resources to enhance classroom engagement and effectiveness. It will encompass various innovative strategies, including flipped classrooms, gamification, project-based learning, and the use of digital tools, all aimed at fostering a more dynamic and motivating learning environment for students. The following briefly describes the educational project category selected:

Figure 1.
Innovation Project.

Category	Definition	Example
Innovation Project	Initiative that introduces new pedagogical practices or technologies in education.	Integration of technologies in the classro

Note. The chart expale the definition of the category innovation project. Source: Own elaboration.

5. Project

The educational project, titled "Pedagogical Practices and Technological Integration for Teaching English," is designed for 11th-grade students in classes O, P, Q, R, and S, under the guidance of Professor Mitzy M. Marín M. This initiative aims to explore the effectiveness of CLIL approach, blending innovative pedagogical practices with technology among others, ultimately enhancing the learning experience and improving English language acquisition.

Our approach focuses on creating an engaging and motivational environment where students can thrive. We will utilize a variety of digital tools, including Microsoft Teams, Moodle, Miro, Canva, Padlet, Edpuzzle, Educaplay, Mentimeter, Quizizz, Mitzy's chatbot AI, Mitzy's Website and so on. These platforms will not only make learning more interactive but will also allow students to express their creativity and collaborate with their peers.

This project seeks to transform the way students learn English by incorporating fun and innovative methods that capture their interest. By leveraging technology alongside effective teaching practices, we aspire to motivate students to embrace the English language in a new, enjoyable, and creative way. Together, we aim to foster a love for learning that will empower our students to succeed in their language journey.

6. Findings from the Verification Process:

1. Positive Elements Identified by the Population

Increased Engagement: Students reported higher levels of engagement and motivation when utilizing digital tools and gamification strategies in their English language learning.

- **Enhanced Learning Experience:** The integration of project-based learning and flipped classroom models allowed for a more interactive and personalized learning experience.
- **Improved Collaboration:** Many participants noted that collaborative projects fostered a sense of community and teamwork among students, enhancing their overall learning experience.

2. Areas for Improvement Identified by the Population

- **Technology Accessibility**: Some students expressed concerns about unequal access to technology, which can hinder participation and engagement.
- **Training for Educators**: Teachers indicated a need for additional training on effectively integrating technology into their pedagogical practices to maximize its benefits.
- **Feedback Mechanisms**: There was a call for more consistent and structured feedback from instructors to guide student progress and improve learning outcomes.

3. Changes to Implement in the Short-Term Refinement Process

- **Enhance Technology Access**: Develop strategies to ensure all students have equal access to the necessary technology, such as providing resources or alternative options for those without devices.
- **Professional Development Workshops**: Organize training sessions for educators focused on best practices for integrating technology into their teaching methods effectively.
- **Establish Feedback Loops**: Implement regular feedback mechanisms, such as surveys or one-on-one check-ins, to gather student input on their learning experiences and make timely adjustments to the pedagogical approach.

These findings and proposed changes aim to refine the project and enhance the overall effectiveness of integrating pedagogical practices with technology in teaching English.

Annex

Pedagogical Practices and Technological Integration for teaching English

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Selected Activities:

1. Introduction to Digital Tools:

- **Microsoft Team or Moodle:** One of these two platforms can be used for managing the virtual classroom. In previous years, we have used Moodle, as it is a very powerful platform designed for educational purposes. However, currently, we are using Microsoft Teams, which was originally designed for corporate purposes and has been adapted for educational use, where a large number of indexed resources have been added.

Since it is the platform allowed by the Ministry of Education, it is what we are currently using with our students. Study materials on the topics we are working on each term will be uploaded, written assignments, videos, and websites will be assigned. Games will be included in different tools to help students improve their performance in class and to allow them to have a broader understanding of the topic to be discussed in detail in the classroom, based on their prior knowledge. Discussions will be held in class about the material placed online.

- **Miro:** It is a visual workspace for innovation where teams of any size can dream, design, and build their future together. I used it with my students in order that they complete assignments and activities designed by the professor online or offline.
- **Canva for Education:** It is a **free upgrade plan for K-12 educators, librarians, and their students**. It provides the power of Canva Pro but is specifically tailored for classrooms. With Canva for Education, teachers and students can create and personalize designs from scratch or use thousands of high-quality, educational templates.
- **Padlet:** It is a **digital communications platform** that helps makes interactions between student and teacher far more engaging and fun. From words and images to videos and links, this digital space can be filled and accessed easily from multiple devices, making it superior to its real-world notice board equivalent.
- **Educaplay:** Give your students the power of **game-based learning** with Educaplay. Do it with your own educational activities, created instantly from your content with the help of our Artificial Intelligence.
- **Mentimeter:** It is a cloud-based polling tool to interact with students through presentations in real-time using a mobile phone or other device connected to the internet. Mentimeter visualises the response data from participants which can be displayed live but it can also be hidden until all students have submitted a response.
- **Quizizz:** It is an interactive learning platform that allows educators to create and share quizzes with their students.
- **Edpuzzle:** It provides a dynamic and secure platform for interactive video learning, making it a valuable tool in modern education.
- **BlackBox AI:** It excels in enhancing the coding process, making it an indispensable tool for developers, data scientists, and educators alike.

Its innovative features like AI Code Generation, Code Chat, and Code Search not only boost productivity but also provide a unique learning platform for understanding and solving complex coding challenges. Using this tool, I create an AI for my students in order to clarify any doubts about the grammar material or any topic did in class.

2. Practical Activities:

2.1 Improving Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing Skills:

1. Edpuzzle:

- **Interactive Video Lessons:** Students engage with video content through embedded questions that test comprehension. This tool is excellent for keeping students focused and ensuring active listening.

- **Pause and Reflect:** Teachers can insert pauses to allow students to reflect and process what they've just heard before responding to questions.

- **Discussion Prompts:** After the video, students can discuss the key points either in written form on Edpuzzle or during live discussions.

2. Miro:

- **Collaborative Mind Maps:** Students can work together to create mind maps based on the audio video or written content, organizing ideas and themes visually or in written way.

- **Storyboarding:** Miro allows students to create storyboards that outline the narrative or main points of the content. They can use text, images, and drawings to illustrate their understanding.

- **Group Discussions:** Miro's collaborative platform enables students to brainstorm, comment on each other's ideas, and build on their peers' thoughts in real-time.

3. Canva:

- **All-in-One Skill Development:** Canva provides templates that students can use to create presentations, infographics, posters, and more. This tool allows them to develop listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills simultaneously. For example, after listening to an audio segment, students can create a visual presentation in Canva that summarizes the key points, which they can then present to the class.

- **Creative Expression:** Canva encourages students to use their creativity to express what they've learned. They can design visual projects that demonstrate their comprehension of the material while practicing writing and speaking skills.

- **Technology Integration:** By using Canva, students not only improve their language skills but also enhance their technological proficiency. They learn how to navigate and utilize digital tools, which is an essential hard skill in today's tech-driven world.

Incorporating these tools into your lessons provides a comprehensive approach to language learning, combining traditional skills with modern technology. Students become more engaged, improve their critical thinking, and gain valuable digital literacy.

2.2 Gamification Using Mentimeter, Padlet, and Quizzes:

1. Mentimeter:

- **Interactive Polls and Quizzes:** Mentimeter allows you to create live polls, quizzes, and word clouds. You can use these features to make lessons more interactive and competitive. For instance, students can answer multiple-choice questions in real-time, and you can display the results instantly.

- **Skills Improved:** These activities enhance listening (as students must listen carefully to the questions), reading (to understand the questions and options), and thinking (as they need to respond quickly and accurately).

2. Padlet:

- **Collaborative Walls:** Padlet provides a virtual bulletin board where students can post notes, images, and links. You can turn this into a gamified experience by having students compete to add the most insightful or creative contributions to a board on a given topic.

- **Interactive Challenges:** Create challenges where students must solve problems or complete tasks collaboratively on Padlet, such as scavenger hunts or brainstorming sessions.

- **Skills Improved:** Using Padlet enhances writing (as students must write their contributions), speaking (when they present their ideas to the class), reading (to understand others' contributions), and thinking (to come up with creative ideas).

3. Quizzes (or Quizizz):

- **Competitive Quizzes:** With Quizzes, you can create engaging, game-like quizzes that students can play individually or in teams. The platform provides instant feedback and ranks students based on their performance, adding a competitive edge.
- **Skills Improved:** Quizzes are great for improving reading (to quickly understand the questions), listening (if used in a listening comprehension quiz), and thinking (as students must think quickly and accurately).

Overall Benefits of Gamification:

- **Engagement:** Gamification makes learning more fun and engaging, which can increase student motivation.
- **Skill Development:** These tools collectively improve listening, speaking, reading, writing, and critical thinking. The competitive and interactive nature of these tools encourages students to actively participate and think critically about their responses.
- **Collaboration and Communication:** When used in teams or groups, these tools also help students develop their communication and collaboration skills.

Gamification using these tools can transform traditional lessons into dynamic and interactive experiences that keep students motivated and actively involved in their learning.

2.3 **Blackbox IA:** It can be a powerful tool in education by providing students with immediate, personalized help. Here's how it can be used effectively:

1. **Grammar Assistance:** Students can ask specific questions about grammar rules, sentence structure, or punctuation. The AI can provide explanations and examples to help them understand and apply these rules correctly.
2. **Material Clarification:** When students have doubts about the material being studied, they can get instant answers and explanations. This helps them grasp difficult concepts and stay on track with their learning.

- 3. Homework Help:** Students can use the tool to get help with homework questions, ensuring they understand the content and learn how to solve problems independently.
- 4. Study Aid:** It can serve as a supplementary study resource, offering explanations and practice questions to reinforce classroom learning.
- 5. Interactive Learning:** By interacting with the AI, students engage in a more dynamic learning process. They can ask questions on-demand, which promotes curiosity and deeper learning.
- 6. Feedback and Improvement:** The AI can provide instant feedback on student queries, helping them improve their understanding and performance in real-time.

Overall, BlackBox IA can make learning more accessible and personalized, supporting students in their educational journey.

3. Evaluation Pattern for Diagnostic, Formative, and Summative Assessments

1. Diagnostic Assessments:

- **Purpose:** To gauge students' prior knowledge and skills before introducing new material.
- **Tools:** Use Microsoft Forms or Quizzes to create pre-assessment tests. You can incorporate interactive elements from CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) to assess both content knowledge and language skills.
- **Implementation:** Distribute the assessments at the start of a unit. Analyze the results to identify areas of strength and weakness.

2. Formative Assessments:

- **Purpose:** To monitor student progress and provide ongoing feedback during the learning process.
- **Tools:** Use Padlet for collaborative activities where students can post their work and receive peer feedback. Employ Mentimeter for real-time polls and quizzes to gauge understanding and adjust instruction accordingly.
- **Implementation:** Integrate these assessments regularly throughout the lessons. Provide immediate feedback and adjust teaching strategies based on student performance.

3. Summative Assessments:

- **Purpose:** To evaluate students' overall learning at the end of an instructional period.
- **Tools:** Use Quizzes or Microsoft Forms to create final exams or comprehensive tests. Incorporate elements from Blended Learning, such as online modules or interactive presentations, for a more integrated assessment.
- **Implementation:** Conduct these assessments at the end of a unit or course. Compare results with diagnostic assessments to measure growth and learning.

4. Observations:

- **Purpose:** To assess student engagement, participation, and application of skills in real-time.
- **Tools:** Use Microsoft Teams for virtual classroom observations. Record sessions or use chat features to note student contributions and interactions.
- **Implementation:** Observe students during activities and discussions. Document key observations to inform future teaching strategies.

5. Self-Evaluation:

- **Purpose:** To encourage students to reflect on their own learning and set goals for improvement.
- **Tools:** Use Microsoft Forms for self-assessment surveys. Provide reflection prompts and questions related to their learning experiences and achievements.
- **Implementation:** Have students complete self-evaluations periodically, such as after major assignments or at the end of a unit.

6. Presentations:

- **Purpose:** To assess students' ability to communicate and apply their knowledge.
- **Tools:** Use Microsoft Teams or Canva for students to create and present their projects. Allow them to share presentations online and receive feedback.
- **Implementation:** Schedule presentation sessions where students can showcase their work. Evaluate based on clarity, content, and use of technology.

7. Student Surveys:

- **Purpose:** To gather feedback on the effectiveness of teaching methods and tools.
- **Tools:** Use Microsoft Forms to create surveys that assess students' experiences and satisfaction with the tools and methods used.
- **Implementation:** Distribute surveys at regular intervals, such as mid-course or end-of-course, to gather insights and make necessary adjustments.

8. Incorporating Technologies:

- **CLIL:** Use CLIL approaches in assessments to integrate language and content learning. For example, include tasks that require students to use specific vocabulary or language structures in their responses.
- **Blended Learning:** Combine online and face-to-face assessments to provide a comprehensive evaluation. Use digital platforms for assignments and in-person assessments for practical applications.
- **Immersive Technologies:** Incorporate virtual or augmented reality tools to create immersive assessment experiences. For example, use VR simulations for scenario-based assessments.

By following this pattern, you can create a robust evaluation framework that leverages various tools and technologies to assess and enhance student learning effectively.

Some examples of Links:

1. **Microsoft Team:** <https://teams.microsoft.com/v2/>
2. **Miro:**
https://miro.com/welcomeonboard/QVBDdGdnc3N6SWRPWW9qR2JYUzlpVktDNUVIQ0M1WHFVMHo0OTV4V1I5b0NPMGFheDNCYXEyRjB5MEJBQXpFUUnwzMDc0NDU3MzQ4OTA3Nzg3NzUxfDI=?share_link_id=722545310382
3. **Padlet:** https://padlet.com/mitzy_marin/quiz-about-present-and-past-progressive-lwo0e1fz28s96r33
4. **Edpuzzle:** <https://edpuzzle.com/media/65665a4a21c647419cb5cb72>
5. **Blackbox IA:** <https://www.blackbox.ai/agent/Mitzy%C2%B4sChatbotKVvLCUh>

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